

Legal and Policy Framework of Artistic Research in Spanish Higher Arts Education

Prof. Dr. Ángel Manuel OLMOS <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8974-684X>

Professor of Musicology- Real Conservatorio Superior de Música de Madrid

1st General Meeting – COST Action 23158

Faculty of Fine Arts – University of Porto

14/15 April 2025

Abstract

This article charts the legal trajectory that has shaped artistic research in Spain's higher-arts sector from the Moyano Law (1857) to the new Ley 1/2024. It shows how conservatories, historically outside the university system, have sought academic parity through a succession of reforms—LOGSE (1990), LOE (2006), LOMLOE (2020)—and the Bologna Process. Recent legislation now grants degrees labelled *Grado* and *Máster*, embeds research competencies in curricula and requires doctoral-level faculty, yet structural asymmetries persist. Regional implementation lags, research funding remains scarce and entrenched studio-master pedagogies resist inquiry-based practices. By mapping these tensions, the study offers a framework for understanding the partial convergence—and enduring distance—between Spain's conservatories and universities, and it outlines lessons for European policymakers working to integrate practice-based knowledge within higher-education architectures.

Keywords: Artistic Research; Higher Arts Education; Spanish Education Legislation; Conservatories.

Historical Evolution and Legal Milestones

Higher arts education in Spain has long existed outside the university system. As early as the mid-19th century, the Moyano Law (Ley de Instrucción Pública, 1857) in its Article 47, recognized for the first time the existence of the artistic studies under the name of "Bellas Artes" (Fine Arts) including painting, sculpture, architecture and music¹. The latter included declamation, the basis of today's theatre studies. Artistic research, or even research alone, was not part of these studies curricula. Not until the late 20th century were comprehensive reforms enacted. The General Education Law of 1970 (Ley 14/1970, de 4 de Agosto, General de Educación y Financiamiento de La Reforma Educativa, 1970) attempted to integrate artistic schools into universities, at the very end of the law, in a transitional provision² that finally was not applied except for the university degree of Licenciado en Bellas Artes and converting fine arts academies into university faculties. However, while the law facilitated the integration of Fine Arts into the university system it failed to achieve the same for music, dance, and the dramatic arts. This discrepancy was not merely the result of legislative oversight, but stemmed from profound institutional, structural, and epistemological barriers.

The integration of Fine Arts (Bellas Artes) into the Spanish university system in the late 1970s marked a significant institutional bifurcation in the treatment of artistic disciplines within higher education. While the

1 "Art. 47. Son enseñanzas superiores. La de Ingenieros de Caminos. Canales y Puertos. La de Ingenieros de Minas. La de Ingenieros de Montes. La de Ingenieros agrónomos. La de Ingenieros Industriales. La de Bellas Artes. La de Diplomática. La del Notariado". "Art. 55. En la carrera de Bellas Artes se comprenden las de Pintura, Escultura, Arquitectura y Música". "Art. 56. Los estudios de Pintura y Escultura son: Anatomía pictórica. Perspectiva. Estudio del Antiguo. Estudio del natural y ropajes. Colorido. Paisaje. Composición aplicada a la Pintura y a la Escultura. Modelado. Teoría é historia de las Bellas Artes. Se agregarán a los estudios de Pintura y Escultura las clases de Grabado que determine el reglamento. El mismo expresará los estudios que han de exigirse para obtener el título de Profesor de cada una de estas partes". "Art. 58. Los estudios de Maestro compositor de Música son los siguientes: Estudio de la Melodía. Contrapunto. Fuga. Estudio de la Instrumentación. Composición religiosa. Composición dramática. Composición instrumental. Historia crítica del Arte musical. Composición libre.

2 Transitional provision Second.Four "Las Escuelas Superiores de Bellas Artes, los Conservatorios de Música y las Escuelas de Arte Dramático se incorporarán a la Educación universitaria en sus tres ciclos, en la forma y con los requisitos que reglamentariamente se establezcan." ("The Higher Schools of Fine Arts, the Conservatories of Music and the Schools of Dramatic Art shall be incorporated into university education in its three cycles, in the manner and with the requirements established by regulation.")

disciplines of music, theatre, and dance remained in non-university higher education institutions—largely conservatoires—the Fine Arts were formally transformed into university faculties by virtue of (Real Decreto 988/1978, de 14 de Abril, Sobre Transformación de Las Escuelas Superiores de Bellas Artes de Barcelona, Bilbao, Madrid, Sevilla y Valencia En Facultades de Las Respectivas Universidades., 1978).

This decree followed the transitional provisions of the (Ley 14/1970, de 4 de Agosto, General de Educación y Financiamiento de La Reforma Educativa, 1970), which envisaged the reorganisation of post-secondary education. Article 1 of the 1978 decree states explicitly:

“The Higher Schools of Fine Arts of Barcelona, Bilbao, Madrid, Seville and Valencia, which were incorporated respectively into the Universities of Barcelona, Bilbao Complutense de Madrid, Seville and Valencia, are transformed into University Faculties, under the name of Faculties of Fine Arts.”³

This transformation was not symbolic; it entailed full inclusion into the university ecosystem, as stipulated in Article 2:

“The Faculties of Fine Arts mentioned in the previous article shall be subject, for all purposes, to the rules of the specific Statute of the University to which they have been incorporated.”⁴

Several factors facilitated this shift:

1. Theoretical Integration and Humanistic Legitimacy

The Fine Arts curriculum already included a strong theoretical and historical component, which aligned well with the epistemological expectations of the university. Courses in art history, aesthetics, and pedagogy had long complemented studio practice, enabling Fine Arts to be framed as both a discipline of creation and a field of scholarly inquiry. This dual status gave Fine Arts an advantage over conservatoire-based disciplines, which remained focused primarily on technical mastery and performance.

2. Alignment with University Teaching Structures

Unlike conservatoires, Fine Arts schools had developed teaching staff with academic credentials, some of whom had earned doctorates or licentiates in humanities-related fields. The 1978 decree allowed the integration of existing faculty into university departments, while also providing a pathway to staff these faculties with university-ranking professors, as established in Article 5:

“The teaching staff of these new Centres will be made up of civil servants belonging to the bodies of full professors, associate professors and associate university professors, and of assistant professors and other contracted professors, in accordance with the provisions of article one hundred and fourteen of the General Law on Education.”⁵

This made Fine Arts structurally and administratively compatible with university norms, unlike music and dramatic arts, where the teaching corps was primarily composed of professional artists, often lacking the credentials needed for academic appointments under the LGE.

3. Strategic Fit within University Missions

There was also a strategic alignment between the aims of the Fine Arts faculties and the broader missions of the universities. The Preamble of the Decree noted the social and cultural value of Fine Arts as contributing to:

3 “Las Escuelas Superiores de Bellas Artes de Barcelona, Bilbao, Madrid, Sevilla y Valencia, que se incorporaron respectivamente a las Universidades de Barcelona, Bilbao Complutense de Madrid, Sevilla y Valencia, se transforman en Facultades Universitarias, con la denominación de Facultades de Bellas Artes”

4 “Las Facultades de Bellas Artes mencionadas en el artículo anterior quedarán sujetas, a todos los efectos, a las normas del Estatuto singular de la Universidad a la que se han incorporado.”

5 “El profesorado de estos nuevos Centros, estará constituido por funcionarios pertenecientes a los Cuerpos de Catedráticos Numerarios, Profesores agregados y Profesores adjuntos de Universidad, y por Profesores ayudantes y otros Profesores contratados, de conformidad con lo dispuesto en el artículo ciento catorce de la Ley General de Educación.”

“Bearing in mind, on the other hand, that the fundamental objectives of the aforementioned Centres are, among others, the conservation and expansion of the artistic-cultural heritage, aesthetic education and the technical-scientific training of the individual in the professional field of pure art, applied aesthetics or the graphic-plastic teaching of the student, it seems appropriate to transform them into University Faculties, dictating at the same time, and in accordance with the aforementioned fourth paragraph of the second transitory provision of the General Education Act, the appropriate regulations for the effective incorporation of the said Centres into the University.”⁶

Such goals dovetailed with university mandates in cultural preservation, knowledge production, and professional training—objectives not as easily transferable from conservatoire-based education, which remained vocational in orientation and pedagogically distinct.

4. Logistical Feasibility

From an infrastructural perspective, the integration of Fine Arts was easier to accommodate within existing university campuses. The requirements of visual arts—studios, workshops, lecture halls—posed fewer challenges than the specialised rehearsal spaces, acoustically treated environments, and performance venues needed for music and theatre training. The latter often require purpose-built infrastructure and specific acoustic and spatial conditions that are difficult to retrofit within general university facilities.

5. Pedagogical Models, Resource Constraints, and Institutional Identity

Another structural challenge impeding the integration of conservatoire-based disciplines into the university system stems from the prevalent pedagogical model of individualized, one-to-one instruction central to music education. In many cases, particularly in vocal performance, students receive individualised instruction from multiple faculty members, such as a principal voice teacher, a répétiteur or piano accompanist, and a diction or phonetics coach for foreign languages. Even in theoretical subjects, classroom size is legally capped at 15 students to maintain specialised attention.

While this model is pedagogically effective, it significantly increases the per-student cost of instruction, creating an economic barrier to university integration. Universities, particularly within the public sector, operate under tight resource constraints, and such high staff-to-student ratios would be difficult to sustain within standard university funding models.

Furthermore, cultural and professional tensions present additional complexities for this potential integration. Many conservatoire professors—often acclaimed performers with extensive professional credentials—do not hold the academic qualifications traditionally required for university faculty positions, such as doctorates. This credential gap has led to ambivalence within the conservatoire sector itself regarding integration into the university framework. Some professionals express concern that such a move could undermine their current status within their institutions, where they occupy central and influential positions. As a result, there exists a sentiment—articulated discreetly though persistently—that it is preferable to be a leading figure in a smaller domain than a marginalised one in a larger, more complex academic structure.

The core challenge lay in the conservatoire model of artistic education that prevailed in Spain, especially in the fields of music and theatre. These institutions operated under a master-apprentice pedagogical framework, prioritising the transmission of practical skills, technical mastery, and interpretive performance⁷. The emphasis on practice over theory meant that research, critical inquiry, and scholarly publication—cornerstones of the university model—were largely absent from conservatoire curricula.

6 “Teniendo en cuenta, por otra parte, que los mencionados Centros tienen como objetivos fundamentales, entre otros, la conservación y expansión del patrimonio artístico-cultural, la educación estética y la formación técnico científica del individuo en el campo profesional del arte puro, de la estética aplicada o de la docencia gráfico plástica del alumno, parece conveniente transformarlos en Facultades Universitaria dictando al mismo tiempo, y de conformidad con el ya citado párrafo cuarto de la disposición transitoria segunda de la Ley General de Educación, las normas apropiadas para la efectiva incorporación de dichos Centros a la Universidad.”

7 Ley 14/1970, art. 28–35

Consequently, the pedagogical culture of these institutions was incompatible with the academic standards and research orientation of the university.

A critical consequence of this structural divergence was that most conservatoire professors lacked the university qualifications required to be absorbed into the higher education system. While many were highly accomplished artists—renowned performers, composers, conductors, or actors—their professional credentials were seldom accompanied by academic degrees or research experience. The 1970 law required university faculty to hold doctorates or equivalent academic qualifications, and made no provision for recognising artistic excellence as a form of scholarly merit.

Spain lacked a mechanism for formally valuing professional artistic trajectories within the higher education system. Thus, no bridge was established to transition established artists into academia, nor were there structured training paths to enable them to meet academic criteria over time.

Additionally, conservatoires remained administratively detached from the university system, under the jurisdiction of regional education ministries rather than national higher education governance. This separation entrenched their marginality and created further obstacles to collaboration, accreditation, and student mobility between universities and conservatoires.

Perhaps most crucially, the broader lack of a recognised discourse on artistic research played a decisive role. At the time, there was no robust conceptual framework in Spain that validated research-through-practice or artistic inquiry as legitimate scholarly activity. Universities, with their focus on written, peer-reviewed knowledge, did not regard performative practices as valid research outputs. This epistemological divide not only prevented the inclusion of conservatoires in the university system but also delayed the development of artistic research as a credible academic field in Spain for decades. The lack of formal education of conservatory teachers on research at large and on performative research in particular, also set an obstacle for the artistic research, even creating misunderstandings on the basic meaning of performative research, as we will see later.

It would not be until the reforms of the early 21st century—including the Organic Law on Education (Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación, 2006) (LOE) and the (Ley Orgánica 3/2020, de 29 de Diciembre, Por La Que Se Modifica La Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación., 2020) (LOMLOE), and the slow incorporation of the European Higher Education Area principles into artistic degrees—that this historical segregation began to be reconsidered. Yet even today, the legacy of this institutional exclusion continues to shape the precarious status of artistic research and the limited research capacities of higher arts education institutions in Spain.

The watershed came with the (Ley Orgánica 1/1990, de 3 de Octubre, de Ordenación General Del Sistema Educativo, 1990) (LOGSE) for the first time incorporated these studies as “enseñanzas de régimen especial” (special studies) within the education system. It established “títulos superiores” (higher degrees) in music, dance, drama, conservation-restoration, and design – explicitly declaring them equivalent to university degrees (generally equivalent to *Diplomado* (undergraduate diploma) and, for Higher Degrees in Music and Performing Arts, to the *Licenciado* degree). Despite formally equating these diplomas to university titles, LOGSE did not fully transform their institutional nature: the studies remained structured like secondary education (with limited academic autonomy and research), and the faculty receive the same salary and scholarly career evaluation as secondary education teachers. Basically, research was not included in any of the evaluation dimensions and incentives for conducting research were not in place as the usual profile of a conservatory teacher didn’t include a doctorate or even a master’s degree.

In 1995, a reform law (Ley Orgánica 9/1995, de 20 de Noviembre, de La Participación, La Evaluación y El Gobierno de Los Centros Docentes, 1995) (LOPEG) went a step further by encouraging, in an additional provision, the development of research programs in arts education – marking the first explicit legal reference to research in conservatories, again in a hidden additional provision: “Fourth additional provision. Higher centres of artistic education. The higher centres of artistic education shall promote research

programmes in the field of their own disciplines.”⁸. However, promote is quite different to deploy. Research activities were scarcely implemented, largely remaining aspirational. Professors typically argue that their official teaching schedules do not allocate sufficient time for conducting research, resulting in research being undertaken voluntarily, often during their personal free time. . Research metrics are not in place, not creating the necessary incentives.

The early 2000s saw incremental changes. The short-lived (Ley Orgánica 10/2002, de 23 de Diciembre, de Calidad de La Educación, 2002) (LOCE) maintained the status quo of 1990, leaving higher arts studies outside the Bologna Process then underway in Europe. Exclusion from the emerging European Higher Education Area (EHEA) was viewed as problematic by 2003.

By maintaining the institutional and curricular framework inherited from the LOGSE (1990), the LOCE effectively relegated higher arts education to a parallel track, structurally distinct from universities and incompatible with the Bologna three-cycle degree system (Bachelor–Master–Doctorate).

This exclusion became increasingly problematic for several reasons:

1. Mobility and International Recognition: Students graduating from Spanish conservatoires and higher arts institutions could not have their degrees automatically recognised in other EHEA countries, as these studies were not aligned with the Bologna framework. This severely limited international mobility, especially for students seeking postgraduate opportunities abroad.
2. Lack of Access to the Third Cycle (Doctorate): Because artistic higher education was not included in the university system, students completing a full course of higher artistic studies had no formal access to doctoral programs. This situation blocked academic careers, especially for those seeking to conduct artistic research or to pursue teaching and research positions in universities⁹.
3. Fragmentation and Inequity: The EHEA was designed to create a coherent, transparent, and inclusive space for higher education in Europe. Excluding a whole sector of knowledge—artistic and practice-based research—from this process introduced systemic inequities and undermined the principle of parity of esteem among disciplines. In Spain, this led to a two-tiered higher education system, where the arts were institutionally marginalised and perceived as lacking academic legitimacy.
4. Loss of Competitiveness and Funding Opportunities: EHEA alignment was increasingly linked to access to European funding mechanisms, including Erasmus programs, Horizon research funding, and other mobility and development instruments. Spanish artistic institutions outside the university system were at a clear disadvantage when trying to access these resources or establish collaborative networks at the European level.
5. Absence of Research Infrastructure and Institutional Development: The EHEA promoted the integration of research and teaching, the formation of quality assurance systems, and the development of internal governance structures aligned with European standards. By excluding the higher arts institutions from this process, the development of research culture in conservatoires and schools of the arts stagnated, with no doctoral programs, no recognised research output frameworks, and no systematic evaluation mechanisms.

By 2003, these limitations were explicitly recognised by the arts education community, which began to advocate more vocally for integration into the EHEA. Reports from the ANECA (Agencia Nacional de Evaluación de la Calidad y Acreditación) and various regional initiatives (notably in Catalonia and the Basque Country) also pointed to the need for a more coherent alignment of higher arts education with university

8 “Disposición adicional cuarta. De los centros superiores de enseñanzas artísticas. Los centros superiores de enseñanzas artísticas fomentarán los programas de investigación en el ámbito de las disciplinas que les sean propias.”

9 Just as a personal note, after finishing my studies in Musicology at the Royal Conservatory of Music in Madrid, I applied to a doctoral program at Sorbonne University in Paris. I was accepted because I had studied Mining Engineering at the Polytechnic University of Madrid, as the conservatory degree was not recognized in France.

standards. This momentum eventually contributed to the LOE (2006) and the Royal Decree 1614/2009, which attempted—albeit imperfectly—to bring higher arts education into the orbit of the EHEA by creating *Grado* and *Máster* titles in the arts, while still keeping the institutions outside the formal university system.

The decisive shift came with the (Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación, 2006) (LOE). The LOE established a separate legal category for “enseñanzas artísticas superiores” as a form of higher education - on par with university-. It grouped the same disciplines (music, dance, drama, design, conservation/restoration, etc.) under this heading and affirmed they are higher education with special organizational demands. Crucially, LOE introduced new possibilities: creation of a national Arts Education Council (*Consejo Superior de Enseñanzas Artísticas*), collaboration with the University Coordination Council on academic planning, and the offer of postgraduate studies (master’s), fully equivalent to university postgraduate degrees. It also allowed partnerships with universities so that art schools could participate in doctoral programs in artistic fields. Article 58.6 of LOE mandated that “*Higher education institutions in the arts shall promote research programmes in the field of their own disciplines.*”¹⁰ – a clear directive to promote artistic research. Articles 58.7 and 58.8 were added by means of the Article 46 of the (Ley Orgánica 8/2013, de 9 de Diciembre, Para La Mejora de La Calidad Educativa, 2013). Article 58.7 enabled the educational Administrations to assign centers of Higher Artistic Education by means of agreement to the Universities, according to what is indicated in Article 11 of the (Ley Orgánica 6/2001, de 21 de Diciembre, de Universidades, 2001)¹¹. Article 58.8 Enabled the educational Administrations to establish procedures to favor the autonomy and to facilitate the organization and management of the Conservatories and Higher Schools of Artistic Education. However a third and final modification of this article 58 removed all those possibilities, as the new law 1/2024 -that we will address later- developed those contents¹².

Despite these advances, LOE still left many aspects to be developed by regulation and maintained that the basic degree structure and faculty hiring followed non-university norms.

Regulatory development soon followed. (Real Decreto 1614/2009, de 26 de Octubre, Por El Que Se Establece La Ordenación de Las Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores Reguladas Por La Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación, 2006) established the detailed framework for higher arts education in alignment with Bologna. It structured studies into *Grado* (Bachelor-equivalent) and *Postgrado* (Master), and even provided for *Doctorate* “in the realm of [arts] disciplines via agreements with universities”). The decree introduced ECTS credit systems, curriculum guidelines, and required a Final Project for undergraduate degrees. It explicitly provided for Master’s programs in art schools and envisioned doctoral studies organized through university partnerships. For example, Chapter II of RD 1614/2009 recognized three cycles (Bachelor, Master, Doctorate) for arts studies, while Additional Provision 5 reiterated that centers should promote research programs, in accordance with LOE’s mandate. A 2015 reform (Real Decreto 21/2015, de 23 de Enero, Por El Que Se Modifica El Real Decreto 1614/2009, de 26 de Octubre, Por El Que Se Establece La Ordenación de Las Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores Reguladas Por La Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación, 2015) updated this framework, making minor adjustments (such as credit ranges for Master’s thesis/projects to facilitate implementation. However, Master degrees in Spanish

10 “Los centros superiores de enseñanzas artísticas fomentarán programas de investigación en el ámbito de las disciplinas que les sean propias”

11 “Artículo 11. Centros de educación superior adscritos a universidades. 1. La adscripción mediante convenio a una universidad pública de centros docentes de titularidad pública o privada para impartir estudios conducentes a la obtención de títulos de carácter oficial y validez en todo el territorio nacional requerirá la aprobación de la Comunidad Autónoma, a propuesta del Consejo de Gobierno de la universidad, previo informe favorable de su Consejo Social.” (“Article 11. Higher education centres attached to universities. 1. The affiliation by agreement to a public university of publicly or privately owned teaching centres to provide studies leading to qualifications of an official nature and valid throughout the national territory shall require the approval of the Autonomous Community, at the proposal of the Governing Council of the university, following a favourable report from its Social Council.”)

12 Today’s text of Article 58, after being modified by the Law 1/2024 is: “Artículo 58. Regulación de las enseñanzas artísticas superiores. Las enseñanzas artísticas superiores se regularán por la Ley 1/2024, de 7 de junio, por la que se regulan las enseñanzas artísticas superiores y se establece la organización y equivalencias de las enseñanzas artísticas profesionales y su normativa de desarrollo reglamentario, además de por los preceptos de la presente ley orgánica que les sean de aplicación.” (“Article 58. Regulation of the higher artistic teachings. The higher artistic teachings shall be regulated by Law 1/2024, of June 7, by which the higher artistic teachings are regulated and the organization and equivalences of the professional artistic teachings are established and its regulations of regulatory development, in addition to the precepts of the present organic law that are applicable to them.”)

conservatories were not offered to students until almost a decade after RD 1614/2009, due to the paperwork, teaching capacity of conservatories, and qualification processes.

During the 2010s, the integration of these studies into national qualification frameworks was also addressed. (Real Decreto 1027/2011, de 15 de Julio, Por El Que Se Establece El Marco Español de Cualificaciones Para La Educación Superior, 2011) and an amendment in (Real Decreto 96/2014, de 14 de Febrero, Por El Que Se Modifican Los Reales Decretos 1027/2011, de 15 de Julio, Por El Que Se Establece El Marco Español de Cualificaciones Para La Educación Superior (MECES), y 1393/2007, de 29 de Octubre, Por El Que Se Establece La Ordenación de Las Enseñanzas Universitarias Oficiales, 2014a) clarified that the Título de Grado en Enseñanzas Artísticas is at MECES Level 2 (equivalent to Bachelor) and Master en Enseñanzas Artísticas at Level 3 (Master), ensuring formal equivalence with university degrees. However, art schools themselves still lacked authority to award doctoral degrees; doctoral study remained under university regulations (Real Decreto 99/2011, de 28 de Enero, Por El Que Se Regulan Las Enseñanzas Oficiales de Doctorado, 2011).

The decree's assignment of the term *Grado* to non-university artistic education institutions was met with immediate resistance from Spanish universities and academic authorities. The Council of Universities (Consejo de Universidades) expressed concern that using identical terminology for degrees from institutions governed by distinct academic standards, governance, and research requirements could lead to confusion of terminology and academic and professional expectations. University rectors and faculty associations feared that this would blur the lines between traditional academic training and conservatoire-based professional education, which historically had different curricula, evaluation criteria, and research cultures.

This concern was intensified by the lack of research structures, doctoral programs, and qualified teaching staff with doctorates in most higher artistic education institutions. As a result, the universities argued that granting the same title to degrees awarded by institutions that were not subject to the same evaluation and accreditation systems could undermine public trust in the entire higher education system.

In January 2012, the Spanish Supreme Court (Tribunal Supremo) ruled against the use of *Grado* for higher artistic education qualifications, declaring null and void several articles of RD 1614/2009, which had previously equated these studies with *Grado* and *Máster* degrees. The Court found that such terminology could create legal uncertainty and mislead students and employers, as artistic education was governed by the Ministry of Education and not by university legislation (*STS 348/2012*, 2012).

This legal decision necessitated the publication of (Real Decreto 96/2014, de 14 de Febrero, Por El Que Se Modifican Los Reales Decretos 1027/2011, de 15 de Julio, Por El Que Se Establece El Marco Español de Cualificaciones Para La Educación Superior (MECES), y 1393/2007, de 29 de Octubre, Por El Que Se Establece La Ordenación de Las Enseñanzas Universitarias Oficiales, 2014b), which amended the MECES framework by specifying that the degrees granted by higher artistic education institutions would be recognised at Level 2 and Level 3, corresponding to *Grado* and *Máster*, respectively, but with distinct titles: *Título Superior de Enseñanzas Artísticas* and *Máster en Enseñanzas Artísticas*, rather than *Grado* and *Máster Universitario*. The Government recognized that the original Decree was not well done and they set the path for fixing the issue (Álvarez, 2012).

However, this cautious compromise created persistent confusion and dissatisfaction among stakeholders, particularly as institutions across Europe increasingly adopted a standardized Bologna nomenclature, aimed at facilitating mobility and international recognition. The issue remained unresolved until the approval of (Real Decreto 628/2022, de 26 de Julio, Por El Que Se Modifican Varios Reales Decretos Para La Aplicación de La Ley Orgánica 3/2020, de 29 de Diciembre, Por La Que Se Modifica La Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación, a Las Enseñanzas Artísticas y Las Enseñanzas Deportivas, y La Adecuación de Determinados Aspectos de La Ordenación General de Dichas Enseñanzas, 2022), which modified several prior regulations to adapt them to the reforms introduced by (Ley Orgánica 3/2020, de 29 de Diciembre, Por La Que Se Modifica La Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación., 2020) (LOMLOE).

For the first time in the Spanish legal corpus, RD 628/2022 explicitly establishes the title of “Grado en Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores” as the official degree awarded by conservatoires and other higher artistic institutions. The decree modifies the earlier (Real Decreto 1850/2009, de 4 de Diciembre, Sobre Expedición de Títulos Académicos y Profesionales Correspondientes a Las Enseñanzas Establecidas Por La Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación, 2009)—which regulates the issuance of academic and professional qualifications—by incorporating an *Anexo I ter*, which specifies the standard formula to be used on diplomas issued for these degrees, that now names the degree as “Grado”.

Furthermore, in the preamble, the decree clarifies its intention to standardise the terminology in accordance with the new legislative framework and academic equivalency:

“[...] it is necessary to modify in Royal Decree 1850/2009, of 4 December, on the issuing of academic and professional qualifications corresponding to the teachings established by Organic Law 2/2006, of 3 May, on Education, the references to Higher Degrees in Artistic Education in order to include the new name of Degree in Higher Artistic Education, both in the model of the degree to be issued, included in Annex I Ter, and in section 8 of Annex IV of the aforementioned Royal Decree in the information table on the National System of Higher Education.”¹³

By introducing this change, Royal Decree 628/2022 effectively supersedes the legal consequences of the 2012 Supreme Court ruling, not by contradicting it, but by creating a new legal basis that had previously been absent. The LOMLOE (2020), which preceded this decree, had already set the stage for such terminological reforms by strengthening the parity between university and non-university higher education and encouraging a more inclusive understanding of academic qualifications across disciplines.

Most importantly, this legal update marked the end of institutional resistance from universities and the higher education establishment. By preserving the distinction through the full label “*Grado en Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores*”, rather than simply *Grado*, the regulation addressed long-standing concerns about terminological confusion and institutional identity, while affirming the academic dignity and European alignment of artistic degrees.

This transition illustrates a broader shift in Spanish educational policy towards a greater inclusion of artistic education within the architecture of higher education, albeit still outside the traditional university system. It also reaffirms the increasing recognition of the specificity of artistic education, which requires flexible, dedicated regulatory approaches that respect both its academic and creative dimensions.

The major recent milestone was the passage of a dedicated law for arts education: (Ley 1/2024, de 7 de Junio, Por La Que Se Regulan Las Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores y Se Establece La Organización y Equivalencias de Las Enseñanzas Artísticas Profesionales, 2024), which regulates higher artistic education and establishes the organisation and equivalences of professional artistic education. This law – anticipated by an additional provision in LOMLOE (Organic Law 3/2020, which had amended the LOE) – is a comprehensive statute addressing the longstanding specific problems of higher arts education. It came after broad consultation and debate¹⁴. The 2024 law establishes a new legal framework granting greater parity with universities in key areas such as curricula, faculty status -now requiring a doctorate for full Professors-, research, and quality assurance. Historical context in its preamble acknowledges that prior reforms were timid and that these studies had been governed by secondary-education criteria despite being equivalent to university degrees. The new law thus seeks to modernize and integrate higher arts education into the higher education system while respecting the creative specificities of the disciplines.

13 Preámbulo: “[...] es preciso modificar en el Real Decreto 1850/2009, de 4 de diciembre, sobre expedición de títulos académicos y profesionales correspondientes a las enseñanzas establecidas por la Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de mayo, de Educación, las referencias a los Títulos Superiores de Enseñanzas Artísticas para consignar la nueva denominación de títulos de Grado en Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores, tanto en el modelo de título que deberá expedirse, recogido en el Anexo I Ter, como en el apartado 8 del anexo IV del citado real decreto en el cuadro de información sobre el Sistema Nacional de Educación Superior.”

14 <https://educagob.educacionfpydeportes.gob.es/lomloe/debate-ley-eeaa.html#:~:text=Educagob%20educagob,alineada%20con%20los%20est%C3%A1ndares>

Curricular Content and Integration of Artistic Research

Curriculum design in higher arts education has gradually moved toward integrating research methodologies, especially since the Bologna-aligned reforms. Under (Real Decreto 1614/2009, de 26 de Octubre, Por El Que Se Establece La Ordenación de Las Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores Reguladas Por La Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación, 2006), all Grado programs in arts must include a Trabajo Fin de Estudios (TFE, analogous to a final thesis/project). Typically, this TFE can be a performance, creation, or research project (or a combination) demonstrating the student's competencies. Research is not required, only an option, and only a fraction of the students submit a research project as they typically are not offered research methodology courses unless they are enrolled in musicological or pedagogical studies. To support this, curricula increasingly incorporate formal training in research methods. For example, conservatory study plans often contain a module on "Metodología e Investigación" in the final year, preparing students to undertake their TFE. At Musikene (Basque Country's Higher Music Center), the 4th-year curriculum for performance majors includes a dedicated subject in Methodology and Research alongside the final project (MUSIKENE Euskal Herriko Goi Mailako Musika Ikastegia, 2018). Likewise, the Royal Conservatory of Madrid (RCSMM) has woven research into its programs: undergraduate students in musicology route engage in research-oriented courses, and all students complete a capstone project. Such inclusion of research methodology courses marks a shift from the purely "professional" training model of the past to a more reflective, inquiry-based pedagogy. However, not all routes and not all conservatories include research methodology as a subject, and still few Professors hold a doctorate and a publication record that allow them to correctly assess and direct the researching efforts of their students.

At the Master's level, the integration of research is more pronounced. Following the legal authorization in 2009, numerous art schools launched official Master's programs that blend artistic practice with research training. The RCSMM, for instance, now offers Master's degrees such as *Máster en Interpretación de la Música Antigua e Investigación y Recuperación Sonora del Patrimonio Musical Ibérico* (Master's Degree in Early Music Performance and Research and Sound Recovery of Iberian Musical Heritage) and *Máster en Enseñanzas Artísticas en Interpretación e Investigación Performativa de Música Española* (Master's Degree in Artistic Teaching in Performance and Performative Research on Spanish Music). These programs explicitly focus on research by their titles, but research subjects are very limited in scope and study time. The curricula include seminars on research techniques, documentation, and writing, culminating in a thesis and lecture-recital. This trend reflects a broader pedagogical shift: rather than treating conservatory training as only craft and technique, Spanish higher arts curricula now emphasize artistic research methodologies as essential learning outcomes. Students learn how to formulate research questions around artistic practice, conduct artistic experiments or scholarly inquiry, and contextualize their creative work within broader knowledge frameworks. However, the traditional lack of education and exposure to research that conservatories have suffered for ages are still present in those research Master's degrees. Performative research, for example, is defined in the study plan as "research on performance" and not "research through performance". When confronted to this misunderstanding, the governing body of the conservatory clarifies that they have defined performative research that way [sic].

The (Ley 1/2024, de 7 de Junio, Por La Que Se Regulan Las Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores y Se Establece La Organización y Equivalencias de Las Enseñanzas Artísticas Profesionales, 2024) cements this integration by mandating research and innovation as central educational aims. It defines among the goals of arts studies "[...] the dissemination and transfer and exchange of knowledge in the field of the arts, as well as innovation and research, in their theoretical, technological, scientific, creative and performative dimensions, and the contribution to economic growth and the promotion of technological sectors, are also highlighted as objectives of these teachings."¹⁵ Moreover, it calls for promoting the learning of research methodologies across artistic disciplines. This means that going forward, every higher arts institution must ensure its curriculum equips students with research skills applicable to artistic practice (such as artistic inquiry methods, critical analysis, and documentation of creative processes). The law even envisions a specialized

¹⁵ Preamble, IV: "[...] se destacan como objetivos de estas enseñanzas tanto la difusión y la transferencia e intercambio del conocimiento en el campo de las artes, como la innovación y la investigación, en sus dimensiones teórica, tecnológica, científica, creativa y performativa, y la contribución al crecimiento económico y al impulso de los sectores tecnológicos."

Master's degree for teacher training that emphasizes research competency (see Section on Faculty Qualifications below), underscoring that knowledge of research methods is now considered foundational for both students and educators in the arts sector.

It is worth noting that the approach to integrating research can vary by discipline. In design and conservation programs, “research methodology” might look more like traditional academic research (e.g. design thinking research, conservation science), whereas in music and dance, practice-based research (investigación performativa o artística) should be emphasized. Spanish institutions have started adopting international models of artistic research: for instance, the Escuela Superior de Arte Dramático de Galicia offers a course on stage research methodology that mirrors the instructor’s own practice-led inquiries (Vieites, 2018). In sum, curricular content across Spain’s higher arts education now is slowly including research elements, fulfilling the legal directives and aligning with European higher education standards of linking teaching and research. “Slowly” is here an important word. The mandate of the new laws of introducing artistic research methodology in all artistic conservatories bumps into a practical issue: the professors teaching at these institutions were never required to demonstrate artistic research skills or education. The Master’s degree that is now compulsory to become a Professor (until the deployment of the 2024 law), needs to show a minimum number of research ECTS, but not specifically artistic, performative, or practice-led research. Not having incentives for incorporating additional research perspectives has led to a situation in which these artistic approaches are usually misunderstood, not understandable and sort of alien. Teaching something that is not well known and that is perceived as marginal and new paves the way of perpetuating this ostracism.

Research Funding Mechanisms for Higher Arts Institutions

Historically, one of the weakest aspects of artistic research in Spain was the lack of dedicated funding. Unlike universities, conservatories and arts schools were not automatically part of national R&D plans or eligible for many research grants, in part because they were administratively under cultural/education departments rather than research ministries. This began to change as regions and the central government recognized the need to support research in these institutions.

Several Autonomous Communities took early initiatives. The Valencian Community stands out as a pioneer: in 2007, Valencia created the Instituto Superior de Enseñanzas Artísticas (ISEACV) to oversee its art schools, explicitly tasking it with promoting research. Article 3(d) of (Ley 8/2007, de 2 de Marzo, de Ordenación de Centros Superiores de Enseñanzas Artísticas y de La Creación Del Instituto Superior de Enseñanzas Artísticas de La Comunitat Valenciana, 2007) charges ISEACV with setting research lines for the various arts disciplines, and an additional provision in that law ensured that *regional research grant calls include the field of higher arts education* “Third additional provision. Scholarships and grants. 1. Calls for research projects and grants made by the Generalitat shall also include the material scope of higher level artistic education. 2. Within the sphere of competence of the Generalitat, the grants for which students in higher artistic education centres may apply shall be put on an equal footing with those of the university system.¹⁶” In practice, this meant that when the Generalitat Valenciana offered competitive research projects or scholarships (traditionally open to universities), conservatory and arts school faculty could apply in categories relevant to music, performing arts, design, etc. – a significant step to fund artistic research.

Other regions eventually followed. For example, Catalonia’s government (also called “Generalitat” as in the Valencian case) through its cultural and education departments has supported research via project grants and subsidies for artistic creation with research components: The Institut del Teatre collaborates with various universities and cultural institutions to promote research in contemporary theatre studies. For instance, the Teatre Lliure, in partnership with the University of Barcelona’s Faculty of Philology and Communication, has established awards for outstanding undergraduate and master’s theses in

16 “Disposición adicional tercera. Becas y ayudas. 1. En las convocatorias de proyectos y becas de investigación que realice la Generalitat también se incluirá el ámbito material objeto de las enseñanzas artísticas de grado superior. 2. En el ámbito competencial de la Generalitat, se equiparán las becas a las que pueden optar los estudiantes de los centros superiores de enseñanzas artísticas con las del régimen universitario.”

contemporary theatre studies. These initiatives aim to encourage research in the field of contemporary theatre. The Escola Superior de Música de Catalunya (ESMUC) offers various scholarships and grants to support its students. These include prizes for research work on music. Such support mechanisms are designed to foster both academic and artistic excellence among students.

The Basque Government, after establishing Musikene (Higher Music Centre) in 2001, provided funding for library resources and collaborative research on Basque musical heritage, albeit on a smaller scale. These regional efforts, however, were patchy and not always sustained, leaving many art schools without systematic research funding.

The Escuela Superior de Arte Dramático de las Islas Baleares (ESADIB) established the Espacio de Investigación, Innovación y Creación (ERIC) during the 2012–2013 academic year. This initiative was developed in response to the integration of higher artistic education into the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), aiming to legitimize and promote research programs focused on artistic creation within the performing arts. ERIC serves as a laboratory for the performing arts, with the objective of fostering the formation of research groups and generating innovative and competitive projects. A notable development stemming from ERIC is the creation of the research group "Procesos de creación escénica," which concentrates on contemporary stage creation processes, including methodologies of analysis, scientific foundations, and the poetics of body and voice in performance. The group also explores the pedagogy and creative process of actors, examining principles, techniques, pedagogical models, and the history of interpretative methods. In 2016, ESADIB launched a pioneering research project titled "Artes escénicas, creatividad y neurociencias" funded by the Balearic Government through European Regional Development Funds (FEDER). This project focused on developing three actor training laboratories that explored the intersection of dramatic art and cognitive neuroscience, particularly emphasizing memory as a central concept in the actor's pedagogical and creative process. The outcomes of these research endeavors have been documented in a series of publications.

Madrid autonomous community tried in 2019-2020 to create research groups within the conservatories. However, this initiative was very short-lived. No groups were created because the administrative committees that needed to be created in order to assess and select the proposals never saw light. Applications were all disregarded without any feedback. No similar initiative has been proposed since then.

At the national level, until recently there was no direct analog to the competitive grants that universities enjoy (e.g. Spain's national plans for science and innovation). Faculty in art schools often had to team up with university researchers to access national funds from agencies like the Ministry of Science or the State Research Agency. For example, a professor at a conservatory might appear as a co-investigator on a project led by a university musicology department, or partake in creative research funded through the Ministry of Culture's programs for the arts. This collaborative approach was implicitly encouraged by LOE 2006, which promoted formal agreements between arts institutions and universities, facilitating joint research projects. The problem is that the Universities' approach to research is not the practice-led, or performative as they lack of the technical skills, so collaborations usually end up using the historical approach.

The new Ley 1/2024 seeks to structurally improve funding access. It explicitly stipulates that "The higher artistic education centres will be able to access European, state and regional funding lines for R+D programmes through their corresponding bodies¹⁷". In other words, the law tears down any formal barriers for art schools to participate in research calls. By policy, this means higher arts institutions should be eligible entities for grants from Horizon Europe, Spain's National R&D Plan, regional innovation programs, etc., provided they meet the usual criteria. This formal recognition is crucial – it gives conservatories a legal basis to apply as lead institutions on research projects (something rarely seen before). Additionally, the 2024 law promises an "adequate and sufficient financing framework¹⁸" to implement its provisions. A

17 Article 57.6: "Los centros de enseñanzas artísticas superiores podrán acceder a las líneas de financiación europea, estatal y autonómica de programas de I+D a través de sus correspondientes organismos."

18 "Disposición final décima. Marco de financiación. Con la finalidad de hacer efectivas las previsiones contenidas en esta ley por parte de las Administraciones Educativas, la Administración General del Estado establecerá un marco de financiación adecuado y suficiente."

dedicated funding framework implies that the central government, in cooperation with regional governments, will channel funds to support new research initiatives, faculty development, and infrastructure (e.g. specialized laboratories, digital repositories, and libraries for the arts). For instance, integration of art school libraries into the national inter-library loan network (REBIUN) is mandated to support research¹⁹, and this too requires funding. However, the deployment of Ley 1/2024 will not be immediate. As education depends on the 17 autonomous communities, each of them need to transpose the national law to their own regulations. Until then, the law will not be applied. And politics also play a role here. In some communities, the governing party is the not the same that at the national level, so they resist to apply regulations. The law itself sets a year for creating the deployment calendar. Up to now, no movement has been done in that direction.

In the years to come, we are likely to see increased funding via: competitive research grants (artistic research projects will compete for funding much as scientific projects do), research contracts (art schools partnering with cultural institutions or industry on funded projects), and internal research support (such as seed funds or sabbatical support for faculty research, now justified by the law's recognition of research as an essential function). The law also calls for incentivizing specific areas like projects with a gender perspective or those increasing women researchers in the arts, aligning with broader research policy goals.

Faculty Qualifications and Research Credentials

Faculty qualifications in higher arts education have experienced a significant elevation in recent years, indicative of a shift towards an academic and research-oriented profile more closely resembling university faculty standards. Traditionally, conservatory professors were hired based on professional merit and the *Título Superior* in their art (akin to a bachelor's level) – few held PhDs or specific pedagogical training. The (Ley Orgánica 2/2006, de 3 de Mayo, de Educación, 2006) (LOE) already hinted at raising requirements: it empowered the government to include additional qualifications for arts faculty “given [their] insertion in the framework of higher education”. Indeed, LOE specified that the entry requirements and even hiring conditions might be adjusted to align with higher education norms, and it allowed hiring foreign professionals as specialists even if they lacked formal degrees (to bring eminent artists into teaching). This allowed the hiring of teachers that didn't attain any basic educational degree. A comprehensive overhaul had to wait.

The Ley 1/2024 establishes clear new standards for faculty. It creates new teaching bodies (*cuerpos*) for professors in arts education, analogous to university faculty ranks, and sets minimum degree requirements for each. Article 53 of the law mandates that to teach in higher arts programs, an individual must possess a Bachelor's degree (*Grado*) or equivalent *and* an official Master's degree specialized in artistic research and pedagogy. In other words, the entry-level qualification is now *Grado + Máster*. ensuring that all new teachers have both teaching skills and “suficiencia investigadora” (research proficiency). It mirrors the requirement in secondary education (where a Master's in Teacher Training is required) but tailored to the arts and with a heavy emphasis on research methodology. By requiring this, Spain is professionalizing conservatory faculty training – future professors of music, drama, etc., will themselves have completed research projects as part of their Master's, bridging the gap between performer/artist and researcher/educator.

Furthermore, the law sets a higher bar for the promotion to senior ranks. For the newly defined *Cuerpo de Catedráticos de Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores* (the senior professors), a doctoral degree is required. This is a monumental change: it effectively means that to attain the top academic rank in a conservatory or arts school (comparable to a full professor or *catedrático* at university), one must hold a PhD. The law provides a

¹⁹ Artículo 57.5: “Las administraciones promoverán la creación y mantenimiento de sus bibliotecas, así como la formación de archivistas y bibliotecarios especializados. Asimismo, deben facilitar la integración de las bibliotecas de Enseñanzas Artísticas Superiores en la Red de Bibliotecas Universitarias Españolas (REBIUN), y de los consorcios y redes autonómicas de bibliotecas universitarias, con el fin de facilitar el acceso al sistema de préstamos interbibliotecarios y a los soportes de repositorios y publicaciones de acceso abierto.” (“The administrations will promote the creation and maintenance of their libraries, as well as the training of archivists and specialised librarians. They must also facilitate the integration of Higher Education libraries into the Spanish University Library Network (REBIUN), and the regional consortia and networks of university libraries, in order to facilitate access to the interlibrary loan system and to repositories and open access publications.”)

transition for current staff, but moving forward it professionalizes the corps. This aligns with European trends – many countries now expect conservatoire professors to hold doctorates in music or art – and it also facilitates better integration with universities (since a PhD is usually required to supervise doctoral students or secure research funding). Indeed, the law notes that those seeking to join the professors’ corps must have the specialized Master’s, and those aiming for the *catedrático* corps must have a doctorate.

Faculty hiring and development are also addressed to support these requirements. The law includes provisions for ongoing professional development, encouraging faculty to engage in research and creative work by giving *economic and professional incentives* for such activities. This likely foreshadows a system similar to the university sector’s research merit pay (*sexenios*): in the university system, professors can earn salary bonuses by having their research output positively evaluated every six years. A parallel could be introduced for arts faculty – recognizing, for example, major artistic productions or practice-based research outcomes as equivalent to research publications for incentive purposes. In fact, Spain’s national research evaluation agency (CNEAI) already in recent years developed criteria to evaluate artistic output (artistic research) for university faculty in arts disciplines. Now that artistic creation is formally a core mission of higher arts institutions, one can expect similar evaluation frameworks to be extended to conservatory faculty. The new law’s emphasis that research is an “essential function” of these teachings and must be promoted by administrations sets the stage for such evaluation and reward systems.

It is important to emphasize how this contrasts with the past and with university requirements. University faculty in Spain (under the University Law, recently updated by (Ley Orgánica 2/2023, de 22 de Marzo, Del Sistema Universitario, 2023) (LOSU) generally must have a PhD for any permanent teaching position, and hiring/promotion depends on research credentials certified by bodies like ANECA. Arts education faculty, being under the education system, historically did not go through ANECA or need PhDs. Now, however, the 2024 law integrates quality assurance and accreditation processes that involve ANECA or equivalent agencies in evaluating teaching and research activity of arts faculty. Common quality criteria and indicators will be developed to assess faculty performance, referencing European Standards and Guidelines for quality assurance. This means arts faculty may soon need to demonstrate research activity (be it artistic research, publications, or innovation in pedagogy) to progress in their careers, much as university lecturers do. Additionally, emeritus professor titles can now be granted in art schools to those with distinguished teaching and research careers (similar to universities), signaling a maturing of the faculty role to an academic stature.

There remains the challenge that relatively few current conservatory teachers hold doctorates. Many have extraordinary artistic careers but not the research credentials. The law’s transitional provisions will allow those in “extinguished” bodies (the old *Catedráticos de Música y Artes Escénicas*, etc.) to integrate into the new system. In parallel, more opportunities are arising for conservatory teachers to pursue doctoral studies (often in collaboration with universities, as discussed in the next section). Over time, a demographic shift in faculty composition is expected, with new hires possessing advanced degrees in music or art—potentially including candidates educated abroad in countries with established artistic PhD programs—and existing faculty pursuing additional qualifications or engaging in artistic research projects that could be acknowledged as equivalent academic merit.

Recognition of Artistic Research Outputs

A persistent question in artistic research is how creative outputs – performances, compositions, exhibitions, etc. – are recognized as *research* on par with papers or patents. In Spain’s policy framework, there has been a gradual broadening of what counts as valid research output in the arts context. The 2024 law makes notable strides in legally recognizing artistic creation as a form of research output and ensuring institutional credit for it.

Earlier, under LOE 2006, the concept of artistic research was present but abstract: conservatories were to “*fomentar programas de investigación*” (“*promote research programs*”), yet there was little in terms of evaluating or crediting the outcomes. University fine arts faculties provided some precedent by treating

artistic works as research in faculty evaluations (with external juries assessing the creative work's contribution to knowledge). In 2015, the national research evaluation system (CNEAI) introduced an "Artes y Humanidades" category allowing artistic productions to count for research merit for university professors, which was a symbolic step. However, conservatory teachers were outside that system.

Now, Ley 1/2024 explicitly affirms that the role of higher arts institutions includes contributing to the development of knowledge through both scientific development and artistic creation. It states that aspects like scientific development and artistic-cultural creation, previously not reflected normatively, are to be recognized via economic and professional incentives. In practice, this means if a conservatory professor directs a major artistic research project – say a series of concerts exploring new techniques, documented and analyzed – this activity should count towards their professional advancement or rewards. The law even calls out "transferencia e intercambio del conocimiento" (knowledge transfer and exchange) in the arts, implying that creative works that influence culture or industry are valued as research impact.

Institutionally, the law integrates these outputs into quality assurance and accreditation. Article 58 of the law requires establishing common criteria to accredit teaching and research activity of professors in arts centers. One can infer that criteria will encompass both traditional research (publications, written theses) and artistic outputs (performances, compositions, designs) relevant to the field. Indeed, the text references alignment with EHEA quality standards. For external program accreditation (now mandated periodically for art degrees just like for university degrees), agencies must consider how each institution's faculty and students produce new artistic knowledge. For example, ANECA or regional quality agencies will look at how a dance conservatory documents and evaluates the creative work done as final projects or faculty projects, and whether those are original and contribute to the discipline.

The recognition of outputs also extends to student research outputs. The final projects of students, many practice-based, will likely be archived in institutional repositories (some regions like Catalonia and Valencia have begun collecting digital TFE repositories for art schools). These works – a score with a research report, a design prototype with a thesis, etc. – are considered part of the research output of the institution. The new law's focus on open-access repositories and integration of libraries (ensuring art schools join consortia like REBIUN) is meant to make such knowledge accessible. In doing so, Spain is formally acknowledging that artistic practice generates knowledge, and this knowledge should circulate akin to scientific knowledge.

From a legal standpoint, an important facet is that the 2024 law and related decrees put artistic research on a similar footing to other research in terms of intellectual property and recognition. Faculty engaging in creative research can be principal investigators on projects and sign research contracts. Likewise, any inventions or creations might be managed under knowledge transfer offices if relevant. For now, much of this is aspirational, pending regulatory development, but the direction is clear.

A concrete example of evolving recognition is the Royal Conservatory of Madrid's involvement in doctoral research outputs. While the conservatory cannot grant doctorates, its faculty have co-supervised PhD work at universities that involve artistic performance components. The RCSMM signed an agreement with the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, its professors participate in a doctoral program on "Music – Science and Technology," and with the Universidad Complutense de Madrid, they contribute to a Musicology PhD program, especially in supervising theses on artistic performance interpretation. In these collaborative doctoral projects, a concert or artistic performance might constitute a part of the dissertation results. The acceptance of such work for a PhD is a de facto recognition of artistic output as research. Moving forward, the law's mandate to foster specific doctoral programs for arts (run by universities but oriented to arts disciplines) will likely produce more practice-oriented dissertations, thereby normalizing creative outputs as valid research contributions.

Today's Spain's policy framework now unambiguously treats artistic creation and performance as legitimate research outputs of higher education, deserving of support, evaluation, and reward. This represents a cultural shift in the legal-institutional mindset – from a time when a conservatory's success was measured only in artistic excellence, to a new paradigm where artistic innovation is also measured in knowledge terms (publications, documented processes, scholarly and artistic impact). The challenge ahead will be

implementing fair evaluation metrics for these outputs, a task that quality agencies and the Arts Education Council will undertake in coming years. And a bigger challenge, maybe the most important, is to change the perception that conservatories are alien to research because of their lack of education and experience in research.

Conservatories and Arts Schools vs. University Regulations

Although higher arts education institutions and universities in Spain now both constitute parts of “educación superior”, notable differences remain in their regulatory frameworks. A comparative look highlights where conservatories have been brought closer to universities and where divergences remain:

- **Institutional Autonomy:** Spanish universities enjoy a high degree of autonomy guaranteed by the University Law (they design curricula, manage budgets, govern themselves through collegial bodies). Historically, conservatories had far less autonomy – they were managed like secondary schools by regional education authorities. The 2024 law makes significant progress here: it calls for giving art schools autonomy in organizational, academic, and economic matters, analogous to universities. It even allows creation of new structures like arts “campuses” or networks and emphasizes governance bodies (like Center Councils, similar to university senates) with participation of faculty and students. Nevertheless, universities have the right to confer all academic degrees including doctorates, whereas art schools cannot independently confer PhDs (they must collaborate with universities). This is a fundamental distinction codified in law: doctoral studies “belong to the university sphere,” though administrations are urged to facilitate specific doctoral programs for arts in partnership with universities. Essentially, conservatories now manage Bachelor’s and Master’s degrees much like a faculty within a university would, but for the PhD stage they rely on university infrastructure.
- **Degree Equivalence and Cycles:** Since LOE 2006 and RD 1614/2009, Spain has asserted full equivalence of arts degrees with university degrees of corresponding level. A graduate of a conservatory with a *Título Superior* is equivalent to a university graduate with a Grado; a Master in Arts is equivalent to a university Master. The 2024 law reiterates this “equivalencia plena”.
- **Faculty Hiring and Career:** University faculty hiring involves national accreditation (by ANECA) and typically requires a PhD and research publications. Arts school faculty until now were hired through competitive exams (*oposiciones*) focusing on teaching and artistic merits, often without research. The lines are now converging: new arts faculty must have a Master’s (and eventually many will have PhDs), and the evaluation of their merits will include research and possibly require ANECA or regional agency involvement for program accreditation and faculty credentialing. However, one stark difference remains: university professors (*catedráticos* and *titulares*) are civil servants under the Ministry of Universities or employed by universities, whereas arts school professors are civil servants under the education system of each Autonomous Community. The 2024 law creates new national corps for arts professors and *catedráticos*, which will be part of the national public employee system (with regional oversight). This parallels the university approach but within a different administrative branch. Over time, we might see convergence in evaluation processes (e.g., an arts professor might undergo research evaluation like a university peer). Another difference is that university faculty have traditionally had a lower teaching load to allow time for research, whereas conservatory teachers taught many hours. With research now expected, we may see adjustments to workloads or additional support for arts faculty to pursue research, similar to sabbaticals or teaching reductions common in universities.
- **Quality Assurance and Degree Approval:** New university degree programs in Spain must be verified by ANECA and approved by universities in coordination with education authorities; they undergo periodic accreditation reviews. Previously, art degree programs were simply set by the Ministry (core curriculum) and implemented by regions, without a rigorous external accreditation cycle. The 2024 law changes this – it requires a verification and accreditation system for arts

degrees analogous to universities. It states that the procedure for proposing, verifying, and authorizing new Master's in Arts will be established with mandatory involvement of quality agencies. It also mandates periodic evaluation of programs and centers, with agencies like ANECA or their regional counterparts taking part. In fact, Article 59 of the law requires that study plans be periodically evaluated to ensure they remain effective and updated, something that is not done now. This lack of updating has rendered some studies obsolete, with few students willing to pursue them. This is a major alignment with university practices. The Catalan agency AQU, for example, has already evaluated arts programs in Catalonia on a pilot basis, and now such practice will be nationwide. The difference that remains is structural: the ultimate authority for a conservatory degree is the education administration (Ministry or regional department), not a university governing board. But with the new law, the Arts Education Council and quality agencies play roles somewhat akin to a University Council and accreditation bodies in the university sector.

- **Research Culture and Output:** Universities operate within a strong research culture – faculty are expected to publish, attend conferences, and secure grants; PhD students populate labs and studios, contributing to output. Conservatories must this culture now, but it is not going to be easy. Culture resistance to change is a well-known hurdle for all change-management professionals. The law's emphasis on creating research groups, participating in R&D programs, and even establishing research institutes in art schools is new. For instance, it empowers art schools to create institutes or join existing research institutions (subject to further regulation) to carry out artistic research. In effect, conservatories could form research units similar to university departments or institutes. But until PhD programs in arts are fully realized, one difference is the absence of doctoral students within conservatories – these students currently must enrol at universities. Doctoral students often drive research in universities; art schools will rely on faculty and master's students, plus any collaborative doctoral candidates from partner universities. Over time, if Spain enables a sort of *Doctorado en Artes* through special agreements (as envisioned by law, the distinction might further blur, essentially embedding doctoral researchers in conservatories while the degree is granted by a partner university).

Regulatory convergence between conservatories and universities is happening in Spain: degree structures, quality control, and research expectations are aligned to a greater degree than ever before. The remaining differences are mainly in degree-granting powers and administrative lineage. Significantly, both sectors are now explicitly recognized as integral parts of higher education. The 2024 law reinforces that unity by guaranteeing equal status of qualifications and student rights (for example, art students now have the same rights to representation, mobility, and resources as university students, correcting a historical inequity. The gap in prestige and resource allocation between conservatories and universities is anticipated to diminish as these reforms are implemented; however, achieving a fully research-oriented identity, traditionally associated with universities, may require considerable time and cultural adaptation within arts institutions.

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